

Experimental assessment of intravenous lipid emulsion in the management of acute fentanyl poisoning

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Received 28 February 2026 ♦ Accepted 15 April 2026 ♦ Published 5 May 2026

Citation: Yarabanova I, Dragomanova S, Stoeva-Grigorova S, Hvarchanova N, Kehayova G, Radeva-Ilieva M, Stoychev E, Dimitrova S, Zlateva S, Marinov P (2026) Experimental assessment of intravenous lipid emulsion in the management of acute fentanyl poisoning. *Pharmacia* 73: e189383. <https://doi.org/10.3897/pharmacia.73.e189383>

Abstract

Fentanyl is a highly potent and lipophilic μ -opioid receptor agonist associated with severe neurorespiratory toxicity and a growing incidence of overdose. Although naloxone remains the standard antidote, its relatively short half-life and exclusively pharmacodynamic mechanism of action may limit its efficacy in intoxications involving highly lipophilic opioids. The aim of this study was to evaluate the therapeutic effects of intravenous lipid emulsion (ILE), administered alone or in combination with naloxone, in a rat model of acute fentanyl toxicity. Thirty adult male Wistar rats were randomly assigned to five groups ($n = 6$ per group): vehicle control; fentanyl (0.44 mg/kg, i.p.); fentanyl + naloxone (1.0 mg/kg, i.p.); fentanyl + ILE (20%, 1.5 mL/kg, i.p.); and fentanyl + naloxone + ILE. Survival and clinical manifestations (loss of righting reflex [LORR], catatonia-like behavior, respiratory impairment, and convulsions) were assessed over 120 min. Survival was analyzed using Kaplan–Meier methodology, and nonparametric tests were applied for ordinal outcomes. No statistically significant differences in survival were observed ($p = 0.406$). However, combination therapy significantly reduced the incidence of LORR compared to fentanyl alone ($p = 0.0152$) and produced the most pronounced improvement in catatonia and respiratory impairment scores ($p < 0.001$, Kruskal–Wallis test). In conclusion, combined naloxone and lipid emulsion therapy demonstrated superior attenuation of fentanyl-induced neurobehavioral and respiratory toxicity compared to monotherapy, suggesting complementary pharmacodynamic and pharmacokinetic mechanisms. Further adequately powered studies are warranted.

Keywords

Experimental model, fentanyl, lipid emulsion, naloxone, opioid toxicity, Wistar rats

Introduction

Fentanyl, a highly potent synthetic μ -opioid receptor agonist, is widely used in anesthesia and pain management, but it has also become a major contributor to the global rise in opioid-related morbidity and mortality. In recent

years, its prevalence has risen markedly among individuals with opioid use disorder, contributing to a substantial increase in overdose cases (Hill et al. 2020). Due to its extreme potency—estimated to be up to 100 times greater than that of morphine—fentanyl presents substantial dosing challenges, particularly outside controlled clinical

settings, and is associated with a high risk of severe and rapidly developing toxic effects (Patocka et al. 2024). Clinically, fentanyl toxicity is characterized by rapid onset of life-threatening manifestations, including severe respiratory depression, central nervous system depression, and muscle rigidity (Kinshella et al. 2018; Zoorob et al. 2023).

Although naloxone remains the standard antidote for opioid overdose due to its competitive antagonism at μ -opioid receptors, its relatively short elimination half-life (approximately 60–120 min) limits its clinical effectiveness in the context of fentanyl intoxication (Martin 1976; Bell and Strang 2020; Saari et al. 2024). In contrast, fentanyl exhibits pronounced lipophilicity and prolonged redistribution and elimination phases, with reported half-life values ranging from 219 to 853 min (Bird et al. 2023). This pharmacokinetic mismatch increases the risk of recurrent toxicity following initial reversal and often necessitates repeated dosing or continuous infusion of naloxone. In response to these limitations, alternative and adjunctive therapeutic strategies are under active investigation. Among them, immunopharmacological approaches, including anti-fentanyl vaccines and monoclonal antibodies, have demonstrated promising preclinical results but remain far from clinical implementation (Romano et al. 2025; Tuncturk et al. 2025). In parallel, intravenous lipid emulsion (ILE) therapy is well established in clinical practice as an antidotal intervention for intoxication with highly lipophilic agents, particularly local anesthetics. Its proposed mechanism of action involves the formation of an intravascular lipid phase that functions as a “lipid sink,” sequestering lipophilic compounds from target tissues and thereby reducing their bioavailability at sites of toxicity (Rothschild et al. 2010; Bilvanisi et al. 2024). Given the pronounced lipophilicity of fentanyl, this mechanism provides a plausible pharmacokinetic rationale for considering ILE as an adjunctive therapy in opioid intoxication.

Despite this theoretical basis and the established use of ILE in other toxicological contexts, experimental evidence specifically assessing its efficacy in fentanyl poisoning remains limited, particularly regarding its interaction with standard opioid antagonists. Data on the combined administration of ILE and naloxone in controlled experimental models of fentanyl toxicity are scarce, highlighting a gap between pharmacokinetic rationale and its validation in controlled experimental settings. It was hypothesized that the combined administration of ILE and naloxone would yield a faster, more complete, and more sustained reversal of fentanyl-induced toxicity compared to either treatment alone, owing to their complementary pharmacokinetic and pharmacodynamic actions. The present study therefore aimed to evaluate the therapeutic effect of ILE, alone and in combination with naloxone, in a rat model of acute fentanyl intoxication. This investigation was designed as a pilot study to estimate effect size and variability in preparation for future adequately powered experiments.

Materials and methods

Chemicals and reagents

Fentanyl citrate (Fentanyl-hameln, batch number: 228018), naloxone hydrochloride (naloxone hydrochloride WZF, batch number: 02BZ0422), and a commercially available 20% ILE (Fresenius Kabi, batch number: 10TH8697) were used as investigational substances. All compounds were obtained from certified pharmaceutical suppliers and were suitable for experimental use.

Study design and ethical approval

The present study was designed as a randomized, controlled, preclinical pilot investigation conducted at the Department of Pharmacology, Toxicology and Pharmacotherapy, Faculty of Pharmacy, Medical University of Varna, Bulgaria. All experimental procedures were performed in strict compliance with Directive 2010/63/EU on the protection of animals used for scientific purposes and were approved by the Bulgarian Food Safety Agency (Approval No. 385/07.03.2024).

Experimental animals and housing conditions

Thirty adult male Wistar rats, bred in the institutional vivarium, were included in the experiment. Animals were housed under standardized laboratory conditions, including a 12-hour light/dark cycle, an ambient temperature of 23 ± 2 °C, and relative humidity of $50 \pm 10\%$, in a well-ventilated facility. Standard rodent chow and water were provided *ad libitum*. Following an acclimatization period, animals were weighed and randomly allocated to five experimental groups ($n = 6$ per group).

Experimental protocol and treatment allocation

The animals were assigned to the following treatment conditions:

- Group 1 – Vehicle control: sterile saline intraperitoneally (i.p.) (matched volumes).
- Group 2 – Fentanyl: fentanyl 0.44 mg/kg body weight (b.w.) i.p.
- Group 3 – Fentanyl + naloxone: fentanyl 0.44 mg/kg b.w. i.p., followed by naloxone 1.0 mg/kg b.w. i.p. at 3 min post-fentanyl.
- Group 4 – Fentanyl + ILE: fentanyl 0.44 mg/kg b.w. i.p., followed by ILE 1.5 mL/kg b.w. i.p. at 6 min post-fentanyl.
- Group 5 – Fentanyl + naloxone + ILE: fentanyl 0.44 mg/kg b.w. i.p., followed by naloxone 1.0 mg/kg b.w. i.p. at 3 min and ILE 1.5 mL/kg b.w. i.p. at 6 min post-fentanyl.

In the treatment groups, naloxone was administered 3 min after fentanyl injection to simulate early pharmacodynamic intervention, whereas ILE was administered 6 min after fentanyl exposure to allow assessment of its pharmacokinetic contribution. In the combination group, naloxone and ILE were administered sequentially at the same predefined time points. The timing of antidote administration was selected to approximate early therapeutic intervention after the onset of fentanyl-induced toxicity.

Dosing rationale and drug preparation

Fentanyl was administered i.p. at a dose of 0.44 mg/kg b.w., corresponding to approximately one-half of the reported median lethal dose (LD_{50}) in rodents, to induce a reproducible model of acute toxicity while maintaining partial survival (Yadav et al. 2018). Naloxone hydrochloride was administered i.p. at a dose of 1.0 mg/kg b.w., consistent with doses commonly employed in experimental models of opioid intoxication (Torabi et al. 2014; Goki et al. 2025). ILE was administered i.p. at a dose of 1.5 mL/kg b.w., corresponding to the initial bolus dose recommended in clinical guidelines for the management of systemic toxicity caused by lipophilic agents (Macfarlane et al. 2021; Neal et al. 2021; Lavonas et al. 2023). Although intravenous administration represents the standard clinical route for ILE therapy, the i.p. route was selected in this model to ensure technical feasibility, procedural reproducibility, and uniform systemic exposure across animals (Kosh et al. 2010). All substances were freshly prepared on the day of the experiment and diluted in sterile 0.9% sodium chloride solution. The administered volumes were adjusted individually according to b.w. to ensure accurate dosing.

Observation period, clinical monitoring, and outcome measures

Animals were observed continuously for 120 min following fentanyl administration. The primary endpoint of the study was survival (at 120 min). Survival was defined as the presence of spontaneous respiration and cardiac activity throughout the observation period (Macala et al. 2018). Time to death was recorded in minutes for animals that did not survive. Animals surviving to the end of the 120-minute period were treated as censored observations for survival analysis.

Secondary endpoints included the onset, incidence, and severity of clinical signs of intoxication. Neurobehavioral and respiratory parameters were assessed using standardized observational methods adapted from established experimental models of opioid toxicity (Kinshella et al. 2018; Haouzi and Tubbs 2022). Loss of righting reflex (LORR) was defined as the inability of the animal to regain a normal prone position within 5 s after being gently placed in a supine position and was recorded as a binary outcome (present or absent). Catatonia-like behavior

(operationally defined as catalepsy-like immobility) was defined as reduced spontaneous mobility accompanied by maintenance of a fixed or rigid posture. It was evaluated using a semi-quantitative scoring system based on the latency to forepaw withdrawal in the forepaw bar test: Score 0: no catatonia observed, posture maintained for < 10 s; Score 1: mild catatonia, posture maintained for 10–29 s; Score 2: moderate catatonia, posture maintained for 30–59 s; Score 3: severe catatonia, posture maintained for \geq 60 s (Sanberg et al. 1988). Respiratory impairment was assessed by direct visual observation of thoracic movements and was scored on a semi-quantitative scale ranging from 0 to 2, where 0 indicated normal respiration, 1 indicated irregular breathing, and 2 indicated severe respiratory depression or apnea (Haouzi and Tubbs 2022). Convulsions were defined as involuntary rhythmic or tonic-clonic muscle contractions and were recorded as a binary variable. Whenever feasible, clinical assessments were performed by an observer blinded to treatment allocation.

Statistical analysis

Statistical analyses were conducted using Kaplan–Meier survival curves, with group comparisons performed by the log-rank (Mantel–Cox) test. Ordinal data were analyzed using the Kruskal–Wallis test, followed by post hoc pairwise comparisons with Dunn’s multiple comparisons test and Bonferroni correction for multiple testing. Categorical variables were compared using Fisher’s exact test. Data are presented as medians with interquartile ranges (IQR). A p -value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant. All analyses were performed using GraphPad Prism v9.0 (GraphPad Software, San Diego, CA, USA).

Results

Survival analysis

Survival at 120 min showed descriptive but not statistically significant differences across experimental groups. All animals in the vehicle control group survived throughout the observation period (6/6). In the fentanyl-only group, survival was reduced to 5/6, with one spontaneous death occurring at 97 min. In contrast, all animals in the treatment groups (fentanyl + naloxone, fentanyl + ILE, and combination therapy) survived until the end of the observation period (6/6 in each group). However, Kaplan–Meier analysis with log-rank (Mantel–Cox) testing did not demonstrate a statistically significant difference between groups ($\chi^2 = 4.00$, $DF = 4$, $p = 0.406$). Similarly, no significant trend was observed across groups ($p = 0.479$). These results indicate that, despite apparent differences in survival proportions, no statistically significant differences between groups were detected, likely due to the low number of events and limited statistical power of this pilot study.

LORR

No LORR was observed in the control group (0/6). In contrast, LORR was observed in all animals in the fentanyl-only group (6/6, 100%). In the fentanyl + naloxone group, LORR occurred in 2/6 animals (33.3%), representing a substantial reduction compared to fentanyl alone; however, this difference did not reach statistical significance (Fisher's exact test, $p = 0.0606$). Lipid emulsion alone did not significantly affect LORR incidence (5/6, 83.3%; $p > 0.9999$ vs. fentanyl). Notably, the combined administration of naloxone and ILE resulted in a significant reduction in LORR (1/6, 16.7%) compared to fentanyl alone (Fisher's exact test, $p = 0.0152$), as shown in Fig. 1.

Figure 1. Incidence of LORR across experimental groups. Data are presented as the number of animals exhibiting LORR in each group ($n = 6$ per group). Statistical comparisons were performed using Fisher's exact test. $p < 0.05$ vs. fentanyl group.

Catatonia-like behavior

Catatonia scores differed significantly across experimental groups, as shown by the Kruskal–Wallis test ($p = 0.0002$). Animals in the fentanyl-only group exhibited the highest catatonia scores, indicating pronounced neurobehavioral impairment. Administration of naloxone markedly reduced catatonia scores, whereas ILE treatment resulted in a moderate but non-significant reduction. Notably, combined naloxone and ILE treatment produced the lowest catatonia scores, approaching those observed in the control group, reflecting substantial attenuation of fentanyl-induced neurobehavioral toxicity. Dunn's post hoc analysis confirmed significantly higher scores in the fentanyl group compared to control ($p = 0.0003$), a significant reduction with naloxone treatment ($p = 0.005$), no significant effect of ILE alone ($p = 0.4764$), and a significant reduction with the naloxone + ILE combination compared to fentanyl alone ($p = 0.0013$) (Fig. 2).

Respiratory impairment

Respiratory dysfunction differed significantly across experimental groups, as indicated by the Kruskal–Wallis test ($p = 0.0004$). Dunn's post hoc multiple comparisons

Figure 2. Comparative analysis of catatonia severity among treatment groups.

with Bonferroni adjustment revealed that animals treated with fentanyl alone exhibited significantly higher respiratory impairment scores compared to the control group (adjusted $p = 0.0010$). Administration of naloxone resulted in partial improvement in respiratory function relative to fentanyl alone (adjusted $p = 0.0171$), whereas ILE monotherapy produced only a modest and non-significant reduction in respiratory scores (adjusted $p > 0.9999$). Notably, the combined administration of naloxone and ILE yielded the most pronounced improvement, with respiratory scores approaching those observed in control animals, and the difference compared to fentanyl alone was statistically significant (adjusted $p = 0.0045$). These findings indicate that a combined pharmacodynamic and pharmacokinetic intervention provides superior mitigation of fentanyl-induced respiratory depression compared to monotherapy (Fig. 3).

Figure 3. Respiratory impairment scores across experimental groups.

Convulsions

The incidence of convulsions differed descriptively between groups (Fig. 4). No convulsions were observed in the control group (0/6). In contrast, convulsions occurred in 3/6 animals (50%) in the fentanyl-only group. Treatment with naloxone completely prevented the occurrence of convulsions (0/6), although this reduction did not reach statistical significance compared to fentanyl alone (Fisher's exact test, $p = 0.1818$). Administration of fentanyl + ILE resulted in a partial reduction in convulsion incidence (2/6 animals, 33.3%), which was not statistically significant ($p > 0.9999$ vs. fentanyl). Similarly, no convulsions were

Figure 4. Incidence of convulsions across experimental groups. Data are presented as the number of animals exhibiting convulsions in each group ($n = 6$ per group). Statistical comparisons were performed using Fisher's exact test.

observed in the combination treatment group (0/6), but this difference did not reach statistical significance when compared to fentanyl alone ($p = 0.1818$). These findings should be interpreted cautiously due to the low event rate.

Representative images illustrating the clinical manifestations of fentanyl-induced toxicity and subsequent recovery following treatment are shown in Fig. 5. These images provide qualitative support for the observed behavioral differences between untreated and treated animals, including catatonia, immobility, and restoration of normal activity.

Discussion

In the present study, survival analysis did not reveal statistically significant differences between experimental groups, despite an apparent descriptive improvement in survival in all treatment groups compared to fentanyl alone. This outcome is likely attributable not only to the sublethal dosing—fentanyl was administered at approximately one-half of the reported LD_{50} to allow partial survival—but also to the low number of observed events, with only a single death recorded across all groups, thereby limiting the statistical power of the analysis. Accordingly, survival outcomes in this pilot setting should be interpreted with caution. The selected dose was deliberately chosen to permit observation of secondary endpoints, such as LORR, catatonia-like behavior

(catalepsy-like immobility), and respiratory impairment, which provide a more sensitive and mechanistically informative assessment of toxicity and treatment effects. Nevertheless, the absence of mortality in all treatment groups, compared to one fatal outcome in the fentanyl-only group, may suggest a potential protective effect of both naloxone and ILE, either alone or in combination. In the context of acute opioid toxicity, survival alone may not adequately reflect therapeutic efficacy, as clinically relevant effects often manifest through sublethal neurobehavioral and respiratory impairment (Hill et al. 2020; Patocka et al. 2024). Therefore, evaluation of secondary endpoints provides a more comprehensive assessment of treatment effects.

Fentanyl intoxication is characterized by rapid onset of severe neurorespiratory dysfunction, including central nervous system depression, respiratory depression, and muscle rigidity (Kinshella et al. 2018; Zoorob et al. 2023). Experimental evidence suggests that opioid-induced rigidity involves central noradrenergic pathways, particularly activation of the locus coeruleus (Lui et al. 1989; Lee et al. 1995), in addition to direct effects on respiratory centers. These mechanisms support the use of neurobehavioral endpoints such as LORR and catatonia-like behavior as sensitive indicators of central opioid toxicity. In the present study, LORR proved to be a robust discriminator between treatment groups. Naloxone administration resulted in a marked reduction in LORR incidence compared to fentanyl alone, consistent with its established pharmacological role as a competitive μ -opioid receptor antagonist capable of rapidly reversing opioid-induced central nervous system depression (Martin 1976; Bell and Strang 2020; Saari et al. 2024). Although this effect did not reach statistical significance, the observed trend is in agreement with previous experimental findings (Averick et al. 2024; Vazquez et al. 2025). In contrast, fentanyl + ILE alone demonstrated minimal effect on LORR incidence, suggesting limited efficacy in reversing early neurobehavioral manifestations when used as monotherapy. This observation is consistent with the primarily pharmacokinetic mechanism of ILE, which involves sequestration of lipophilic compounds within an expanded lipid phase ("lipid sink"), thereby reducing their bioavailability (Rothschild et al. 2010; Bilvanisi et al. 2024). While this mechanism may contribute to drug redistribution, it

Figure 5. Representative images of experimental animals. A. Animal exhibiting fentanyl-induced catatonia and immobility; B. Animal showing recovery of normal posture and activity following treatment.

is unlikely to rapidly counteract receptor-mediated central effects in the early phase of intoxication. Notably, the combined administration of naloxone and ILE resulted in a statistically significant reduction in LORR incidence, indicating a potential synergistic interaction between these interventions. This effect can be explained by their complementary mechanisms of action, whereby naloxone provides rapid pharmacodynamic antagonism at opioid receptors, whereas ILE reduces the circulating free fraction of fentanyl, potentially prolonging and stabilizing the therapeutic effect. Such combined pharmacodynamic–pharmacokinetic targeting may be particularly relevant in the context of highly lipophilic opioids such as fentanyl (Bird et al. 2023).

A similar pattern was observed for catatonia-like behavior, which emerged as a highly sensitive quantitative endpoint. Fentanyl administration resulted in pronounced catatonic behavior, consistent with its known central depressant effects and its ability to induce rigidity via noradrenergic pathways. Statistical analysis confirmed significant differences between groups. Naloxone significantly attenuated catatonia severity, although residual mild impairment in some animals indicates that receptor antagonism alone may not fully counteract all components of fentanyl-induced neurotoxicity. Fentanyl + ILE alone produced a moderate, non-significant reduction in catatonia scores, supporting its predominantly pharmacokinetic mechanism of action. Importantly, the combination therapy of naloxone and ILE resulted in the most pronounced reduction in catatonia scores, approaching control levels and indicating a synergistic interaction between pharmacodynamic and pharmacokinetic mechanisms. These findings are consistent with previous reports highlighting the benefits of combined approaches in managing toxicity induced by lipophilic agents (Macfarlane et al. 2021; Neal et al. 2021; Lavonas et al. 2023).

Respiratory impairment emerged as one of the most clinically relevant and sensitive endpoints in this study. Fentanyl administration induced pronounced respiratory depression, consistent with its well-established central effects on respiratory control (Hill et al. 2020). This was manifested through decreased respiratory drive, irregular breathing patterns, and apnea, attributable to activation of μ -opioid receptors in the brainstem (Zoorob et al. 2023). Concomitant fentanyl-induced chest wall rigidity may further compromise ventilation, and additional opioid-mediated pulmonary effects have also been reported (Kinshella et al. 2018; Güney et al. 2025). In the present experiment, naloxone administration substantially ameliorated respiratory dysfunction, confirming its critical pharmacodynamic role in reversing opioid-induced respiratory depression. ILE monotherapy provided only partial improvement, likely reflecting its primarily pharmacokinetic mechanism of sequestering lipophilic compounds and reducing tissue bioavailability. Notably, the combined administration of naloxone and ILE yielded the most pronounced mitigation of respiratory compromise, suggesting a complementary effect whereby rapid receptor

antagonism is supported by enhanced drug redistribution. These findings are particularly relevant for highly lipophilic opioids such as fentanyl, in which prolonged tissue retention may diminish the duration of naloxone action (Bird et al. 2023; Smith et al. 2023). Together, these results indicate that a dual pharmacodynamic–pharmacokinetic intervention may provide both immediate and sustained protection against opioid-induced respiratory depression.

Convulsions were observed in a subset of animals in the fentanyl-only group but were absent in control animals. Although not a classical manifestation of opioid toxicity, atypical presentations, including motor disturbances and dyskinesia, have been described, particularly with potent synthetic opioids (Kinshella et al. 2018). Naloxone and triple combination therapy completely prevented the occurrence of convulsions, whereas the fentanyl + ILE group showed only a modest effect. However, these differences did not reach statistical significance, likely due to the low event rate.

Overall, the results indicate that targeting both the pharmacodynamic and pharmacokinetic properties of opioid toxicity simultaneously may provide superior efficacy compared to monotherapy. This dual approach is particularly beneficial in cases of overdose with lipophilic opioids, which produce immediate central effects while remaining in the body for extended periods.

Several limitations should be acknowledged. The present study was designed as a pilot experiment and was not powered to detect differences in survival or less frequent endpoints. In addition, the use of intraperitoneal administration for ILE, although methodologically justified, may limit direct clinical translation. Future studies with larger sample sizes, optimized dosing strategies, and clinically relevant routes of administration are warranted to confirm these findings and to further elucidate the role of combined naloxone and lipid emulsion therapy in the management of acute opioid toxicity.

Conclusion

In this pilot study, no statistically significant differences in survival were observed between experimental groups, likely due to the low number of events. However, treatment with naloxone and ILE, particularly in combination, was associated with a consistent improvement in neurobehavioral and respiratory parameters compared to fentanyl alone. Naloxone demonstrated a pronounced effect on reversing central and respiratory depression, whereas ILE showed a more limited effect as monotherapy. The combination of both interventions resulted in the most favorable overall profile, suggesting a complementary interaction between pharmacodynamic and pharmacokinetic mechanisms. These findings indicate that combined therapeutic approaches may be beneficial in acute intoxication with highly lipophilic opioids such as fentanyl. Further studies with larger sample sizes are required to confirm these results and to assess their clinical relevance.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

Experiments on animals: Document No. 385/07.03.2024, Bulgarian Food Safety Agency.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) use

The authors accept full responsibility for the content of the manuscript, including the disclosure of any use of AI.

No AI tools were used in the preparation of this manuscript.

Funding

This work was supported by the Fund "Science," Medical University of Varna, Bulgaria (Project No. 23004, Grant No. FS-6/02 February 2022) and the European Union–NextGeneration EU,

through the National Recovery and Resilience Plan of the Republic of Bulgaria, Project No. BG-RRP-2.004-0009-C02.

Author contributions

Conceptualization, methodology, and research: IY, SD, SS-G, NH, GK, MR-I, ES, SD, SZ, PM. Literature search and analysis: IY, SD, SS-G, NH, GK, MR-I, ES, SD, SZ, PM. Data acquisition and analysis: IY, SD, SS-G, NH, GK, MR-I, ES, SD, SZ, PM. Statistical analysis: IY, SD, SS-G, NH, GK, MR-I, ES, SD. Writing of the manuscript—draft: IY, SD, SS-G, NH, GK, MR-I, ES, SD, SZ, PM. Review and editing of the original manuscript: SZ, PM. Final review and approval of the manuscript: SZ, PM.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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